

Short name	Unclear accounting of DAC (negative emissions)	Long name	Lack of clarity where (which sub-sector) DAC is reported in GHG inventories
Geographical scope	International		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>National greenhouse gas inventories serve for tracking developments in national emissions and removals. Direct air capture of CO₂ is a novelty and has not yet been reported in GHG inventories. Accordingly, there is some level of uncertainty regarding where to properly report the CO₂-captured (for durable storage).</p> <p>Furthermore, removals have to date essentially only been recognized in the Land-use sector, it may thus be confusing to report negative values for emissions within a sector sub-category.</p> <p>CO₂-removal from direct air capture may be most appropriately reported under the sector <i>Industry - Category 2.H.3. Other</i>¹.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Pioneering countries including notably Iceland will soon start to capture significant volumes of CO ₂ through DAC. As these pioneers start reporting in inventories, the IPCC taskforce on inventory guidance should adopt corresponding language in the next version that clarifies where DAC should be reported.		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accounting readiness - Project specific monitoring reporting and verification practices 		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poralla, M.; Honegger, M.; Gameros, C. et al. (2022): Tracking greenhouse gas removals: baseline and monitoring methodologies, additionality testing, and accounting, NET-Rapido Consortium and Perspectives Climate Research, London, UK and Freiburg i.B., Germany • Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2019): 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories • Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2006): 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories • International Energy Agency (IEA) (2022): Direct Air Capture - A key technology for net zero 		

¹ This suggestion has been discussed as a possible resolution, which appears fully in line with GHG inventory guidance, but – to the authors’ knowledge is not yet established common practice.